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Managing digital transformation of organizational culture and its shaping factors in the context of digitalization

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The article is relevant due to the development of modern technologies (artificial intelligence, machine learning, and cloud services). Changing business processes and management approaches require companies to adapt and implement digital solutions; these changes are in approaches to management, in interaction with clients and partners and in organizational culture. Digital transformation of organizational culture helps increase the efficiency of business processes and improves interaction between employees and departments.

The article aims to review the processes of managing organizational culture in the context of digitalization.

Materials and methods. The research is based on scientific publications and articles, as well as studies and reviews in scientific journals dedicated to digital transformation, organizational culture, and change management. Research methods include comparative analysis and modeling.

Results. Organizational culture management processes in the context of digitalization are considered. Notably, digital transformation of organizational culture (the main components of which are presented by the authors in the form of a model) in the modern global market is a key condition for the survival of companies. The advantages and difficulties of digital organizational culture are considered separately. The key elements of digital organizational culture and also transformation that arises are analyzed in detail – these processes impact the strategy, structure, and management systems of the organization, aiming to optimize the management system and ensure a balance between personnel and technology. At the same time, the authors emphasize that formulating an overall systemic picture of digital organizational culture is a challenge.

Conclusion. At the current stage of Russia's economic development, digital organizational culture offers certain advantages, influencing formation of the organizational structure and creation of a positive and constructive work environment. It also forces companies to set new goals by changing their activities. As a result, digital transformation of a company's organizational culture can help reduce operating costs, promote new or improved products and services, and enhance the quality of interaction with customers and employees.

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INTRODUCTION

Digital economy is at all times the focus of attention for theorists, practitioners, researchers, and managers at various levels, offering opportunities for digitalization of all processes within organizations, companies, or enterprises, as well as across all spheres of public life. Digital technologies are transforming the world, including human resources management and organizational culture. Artificial intelligence and neural networks are transforming traditional labor relations and the style of interaction in the organizational space into new growth points and opportunities.

On the one hand, digitalization helps improve people's lives, optimize costs, automate operational activities, transfer some tasks online, accelerate digital interaction, and enhance operational quality. On the other hand, even when it is clear what effect a particular technology can have, its full implementation in personnel management may be complex due to established traditional approaches to work and people's resistance to change.

Thus, development of modern technologies (artificial intelligence, machine learning, and cloud services) is changing business processes and management approaches, which requires companies to adapt and implement digital solutions. These changes are in approaches to management, interaction with clients and partners, as well as in organizational culture; in the context of digitalization, employees are seeking to work in companies that utilize modern technologies and offer flexible working conditions. Digital transformation of organizational culture helps increase the efficiency of business processes and improves interaction between employees and departments.

The article aims to review the processes of managing organizational culture in the context of digitalization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The basis for the research is scientific publications, reviews in scientific journals dedicated to digital transformation, organizational culture, and change management; conference and seminar materials, including reports and presentations from professional events focused on digital transformation and organizational culture management.

Research methods: comparative analysis (comparing different approaches to using digital technologies to transform organizational culture and identifying the most effective practices); modeling (developing models to describe the impact of digital transformation on organizational culture, for forecasting and analyzing possible development scenarios).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, few papers [see, for example, 1] examine the specifics of how digitalization affects organizational culture as a whole. Disparate materials address the issues of artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities and training within individual sectors of the economy and areas of activity of particular organizations (logistics, supply, distribution, construction, industry, education, etc.). AI is trained on large datasets from companies, including employee performance and effectiveness, actions and outcomes, as well as other organizational and contextual factors. At the same time, forming an overall systemic picture of digital organizational culture is difficult.

To date, technologies have the required level of development, which allowed them to become widespread within organizations, enterprises, and companies. According to the results of our previous research [2], introduction of AI into an organization can help reduce operating costs, promote new or improved existing products and services, and enhance the quality of interaction with customers and employees. In the medium term, this may lead to a transformation of the organization [3]. However, it is essential to note that the use of AI in an organization can have unpredictable consequences for both the internal and external environments of the company. Positive effects can be offset by negative consequences [4; 5].

V. Velyako and S. Musa write that the biggest obstacle to digital transformation is cultural issues within the organization. According to the authors, digital organizational culture will improve the possibilities of implementing digital technologies in an organization [6].

J. Wang et al. study the impact that digital economy has on the formation of a staff competence model, and the definition of methodological aspects of its implementation in business structures. According to the authors, successful implementation of the competence model in digital economy necessitates new directions for developing an appropriate organizational culture, as well as the effective use of digital educational technologies [7].

J. Erjavec et al. define the primary organizational characteristics and forms necessary for a company's successful digital transformation. The authors believe that decisions about organizational forms should depend on digital culture, the role of the IT department, and the goals of the CT [8].

J. Zhang and Z. Chen believe that five factors (internal digital customer needs, industry-specific digital innovation, competition concerns, digital innovation management, and the needs of the digital age) are driving the digital transformation of human resource management. The authors write that digital human resource management processes are related to such functions as selection, training, development, and evaluation, utilizing modern digital technologies [9].

A. Naimi-Sadigh et al. believe that to implement digital change, organizations require a clear strategy, a proper organizational structure, digital capabilities, a supportive organizational culture, and a balanced management system for implementing digital change [10].

M. Suravaeva & E. S. Popova consider sustainable development as the most critical aspect of holistic organizational development, with the subsequent transformation of internal culture. The authors demonstrate that sustainable development is the outcome of informed and balanced management decisions, informed by critical thinking, an analytical approach, and flexibility in decision-making, which aligns with the objectives of corporate social responsibility [11].

F. Trompenaars and P. Woolliams propose a new conceptual framework for achieving relational rent, in which employees of one organization can communicate effectively with those of another. Cultural gaps give rise to several dilemmas, which, when resolved, provide relational rent [12].

P. Xanthopoulou et al. investigate the key organizational factors that influence the digital transformation of the public sector in Greece. The authors showed that technological factors, which comprise the quality of service, and organizational factors such as training and evaluation of human resources, leadership, organizational strategy, and creation of digital culture, had a significant impact on successful adoption and implementation of digitalization projects [13].

E. A. Bolotova notes that digitalization of education and of areas of intensive life activity reveals a person's formation of a communicative culture that allows them to competently take advantage of the opportunities for organic entry into a specific environment of the information society [14].

D. Yuan et al. suggest that organizational flexibility can significantly mitigate the positive impact of psychological ownership on personal knowledge and social exclusion. As resource flexibility and cultural flexibility increase, the role of social exclusion decreases [15].

Thus, the analysis of existing theories and models of digital transformation and organizational culture allow us to understand the principles and mechanisms of interaction between digital technologies and the organization's culture.

It is essential to develop and refine methodological tools to investigate the impact of digital transformation on organizational culture. It is also necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of introducing digital technologies in transforming organizational culture, as well as their effects on productivity, collaboration, and employee satisfaction.

RESULTS

Digital transformation of organizational culture and its shaping factors

Transformation of organizational culture begins with creation of a “new” company/organization capable of adapting to changes and overcoming crises. The Organizational culture must ensure a balance between people and technology, and successful digital growth requires staff restructuring and adaptation to transformation.

Some Russian-Chinese companies believe that digital transformation requires significant investments and poses risks to organizational culture. Employees associate these innovations with the risk of dismissal and of impact on organizational stability [16].

In today's global market, the need for digital transformation is increasingly seen as a condition for the survival of companies, organizations and enterprises. It is challenging to find a function or process not enhanced with the aid of technological tools.

Any changes in the organization related to digital transformation involve not only adapting to technological innovations but also developing the appropriate professional knowledge, skills, and abilities relevant to the organization's strategy and goals.

Digital transformation of organizational culture and its shaping factors necessitate ongoing adjustments in processes and behaviors. At the same time, digital organizational culture, based on an assessment of the emerging environment, enables a wide range of digital resources and tools that simplify the activities of the organization's employees (see Fig. 1).

Compiled by the authors based on the research materials

Figure 1 Formation of digital organizational culture

Let us define the main components that form digital culture (see Figure 2). Creation of digital culture is based on specific elements: risks, transformation of organizational culture, short-term planning, staff collaboration, and changing outdated organizational systems and structures. Transition to a new digital environment presents potential risks associated with adopting digital culture, both in terms of effective company management and staff collaboration to achieve organizational goals. This enables more flexible adaptation to ongoing processes, thereby creating an appropriate digital environment and, in turn, digital organizational culture.

Digital transformation that determines digital culture depends primarily on the organization's field of activity, goals, strategy, size, core values, and structure.

Digital organizational culture that promotes transformational change, supports innovation, fosters a suitable work environment, and overcomes the limitations of traditional organizational culture is of great importance in modern conditions, characterized by the digital era's conditions of digital transformation, which enables companies and organizations to thrive in the market.

Compiled by the authors based on the research materials

Figure 2 Elements of digital organizational culture

Currently, at least three main problems exist that prevent most companies from successfully implementing digital transformation: risk aversion, functional and departmental barriers, and the challenge of creating a customer-centric culture. As a result, avoiding change and digital transformation in the corporate environment leads to stagnation and degradation. However, some companies successfully develop digital and innovative culture and benefit enormously; Facebook and Apple can be cited as examples [17].

The rapid change, both globally and in Russia, requires that organizations adapt to these changes not only in strategic and tactical areas but also in technological and resource areas. These adaptation mechanisms, based on digital transformation and on practical implementation of digital technologies, influence changes in

organizational culture, which in turn shape its flexibility, openness, and transparency, ultimately determining its potential, significance, and functional effectiveness in these organizational processes.

The company's digital organizational culture provides certain advantages:

1. It influences formation of a flexible organizational structure without hierarchy and horizontally coordinated work processes;
2. It promotes spreading of best practices and encourages individual employees' involvement in decision-making;
3. It develops employees' ability to perform complex tasks and promotes inclusive growth;
4. It creates a positive and constructive work environment by attracting talented employees through collaboration, creativity, and innovation.

Changing the culture of an organization is more difficult than it seems. Digital transformation forces companies to set new goals, adopt new methods, and change their attitudes, behaviors, and practices; these are fundamental changes in the activities of organizations, resulting in numerous and complex problems.

The difficulties of digital transformation of organizational culture

Digital transformation of organizational culture leads to specific difficulties, in particular, lack of flexibility and variability, significant costs associated with implementation and maintenance of the organization's digital infrastructure, redistribution and scaling of company resources for digital transformation, and inefficient automation that does not allow abandoning manual labor and increasing overall efficiency, etc. – fear of disrupting a comfortable environment, doubts about reliability, and low qualifications prevent automation of an organization. Digital literacy is the most significant barrier to change – managers accustomed to traditional business culture are often unfamiliar with new technological processes, and their training requires considerable time and planning [17]. This aspect, related to certain complexities of digital organizational culture, is discussed in more detail in our publications [2].

It is necessary to make fundamental changes in corporate culture in the context of modern digital transformation:

- Evaluating the existing organizational culture and performance indicators to identify strengths and weaknesses, and keeping the “positive” and eliminate the “destructive”;

- Identifying the benefits of changing organizational culture, enabling employees to understand their responsibilities and behavior expected of them;
- Identifying key performance priorities that require focused work and straightforward implementation to promote growth and increase the company's potential;
- Forming a working group of managers who will monitor implementation of priorities, goals, and results. Tracking can also be used for efficiency analysis, job optimization, and resource usage analysis;
- Hiring new employees or increasing the number of staff to complete new tasks and achieve goals through new processes. Introduction of digital organizational culture leads to new challenges that require skilled labor;
- Developing a reward system to maintain the motivation and commitment of employees who contribute to the company's development.

In today's world, there is a growing demand for a culture that is ready to embrace innovation and adapt to new business rules. Implementing this task may require significant resources. Companies that offer their customers a set of digital solutions to improve efficiency have a better chance of success in the market. Organizations that are not adapted to the changes that are taking place run the risk of at least limiting or not increasing financial performance and reducing revenue/profit, which will inevitably affect capitalization of the company, and at most losing market share in favor of competitors with a more flexible and changeable strategy mediated by a more flexible organizational culture.

Organizational changes are a set of measures aimed to optimize the management system (strategy, structure, etc.) to increase the effectiveness and competitiveness of the entire organizational structure. Managerial change management is a mechanism for ensuring, planning, coordinating, training, monitoring, optimizing and implementing change in a company to increase overall efficiency [18, 19].

Various factors can contribute to organizational transformation. Considering the need for and importance of ongoing changes, a key element is transformation of organizational culture, which plays a significant role in facilitating more effective change. At the same time, inversion and innovation of organizational culture are based on values, traditions, myths and basic ideas shared by the company's employees, which should be transformed, thereby transforming and improving the organizational culture to create a new identity for the organization and its employees to increase productivity, efficiency and contribute to solving other specific tasks.

The analysis of cultural change can be presented in the form of a matrix based on the impact of reactive and proactive factors, as well as ameliorative and strategic goals (see Fig. 3).

Compiled by the authors based on the research materials

Figure 3 Elements of digital organizational culture

The main processes of organizational culture change and key elements of their effectiveness

Higher organizational goals in solving social issues are achieved by creating a favorable and inclusive work environment, which is conditioned and predetermined by the organization's culture and cultural changes that are not directly related, for example, to adaptation or the company's survival.

The concept of organizational cultural change assumes that any change goes through three stages (see Fig. 4):

Compiled by the authors based on the research materials

Figure 4 The model of cultural organizational changes

- Unfreezing – the management staff and employees of the organization understand that the common core values, attitudes, and expectations are outdated, and it is necessary to change the organizational culture;
- Motion – changes are implemented with the planned effect (for example, increased productivity or functionality). New components are integrated locally and in small portions (a policy of phased innovation). If successful, the changes are expanded. At the same time, it is necessary to maximize employee awareness;

- Freezing – internalization and consolidation of new attitudes and approaches at the corporate level. This stage can be carried out through various means such as conferences, internships and additional professional training and retraining programs for employees. The primary goal of setting is reflection and consolidation of emerging new organizational values, thereby minimizing the possibility of reverting to the previous organizational culture.

At the same time, the organization/company/enterprise itself goes through the stages of its life cycle: foundation (integration into the environment), early growth (formation of organizational identity), development (culture has evolved and can be either a factor of progress or regression by shared values), maturity (serious problems arise) and decline (need for a total reboot). Depending on the stage at which the company is, a specific set of measures and actions leads to changes in the organizational culture. Gradual changes occur through formation of unique cultural characteristics within small groups, which then spread to higher managerial levels.

Compiled by the authors based on the research materials

Figure 5 The main processes of organizational culture change and key elements of their effectiveness

A certain model of transformation or change in the existing organizational culture is to be chosen over another with obligatory consideration of the transformation context. In particular, it is necessary to identify and analyze relevant factors that contribute to transformation and irrelevant ones that hinder it. According to K. Curren, organizational culture can be significantly improved by following the recommendations that were discussed in detail in our earlier publications [4].

For a successful change in organizational culture, several key factors must be considered (see Figure 5). Cultural change must be supported not only by formal organizational changes but also by real actions; these changes are not possible through ideological or conceptual principles. The recorded formal changes are a derivative of creating a constructive organizational climate capable of absorbing a comprehensive range of cultural changes, thereby generating conditions for adoption of new values.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The planned changes in organizational culture and its transformation into a digital organizational culture should take into account not only consistently implemented strategies that determine the activities of all organizational levels but also the characteristic features inherent in a particular company or organization.

The definition of a new model of the cultural fabric of an organization or a cultural agent of change should correlate with its life cycle and stage of development. Employees responsible for corporate change are to study the stage of development and the company's history to assess its cultural components and determine the next steps adequately.

The conducted scientific research has several promising directions. In particular, development of new methodologies and tools for assessing and managing digital transformation of organizational culture is relevant. It is essential to examine the impact of digital transformation on various aspects of organizational culture, including values, norms, beliefs, and employee behavior.

Scientists are interested in understanding how leaders can contribute to creating a culture that is open to innovation and change, as well as which change management strategies are most effective in the context of digital transformation. Analyzing best practices and cases can help other organizations learn from leaders' experiences and adapt successful strategies to their needs.

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